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RISK OF AUTOIMMUNE THYROID DISEASES DURING OXIDATIVE STRESS

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Annotation. *Currently, a large number of socially significant diseases are known in which tissue damage is accompanied by the development of oxidative stress. Free radicals play a crucial role in the development of these diseases. Similar processes occur under the influence of sources of ionizing radiation, as well as during bacterial infections. Recently, scientific evidence has emerged indicating a significant role of oxidative stress in the development of autoimmune thyropathies. It is assumed that the synthesis of thyroid hormones depends on the concentration of H₂O₂, which, due to its high toxicity, must be in strict accordance with the activity of antioxidant systems. Normally, many biochemically unfavorable processes occur on the apical membrane of the thyrocyte, which makes it possible to limit the action of free radicals and avoid cell destruction. However, under pathological conditions, enzymatic systems are disrupted and their components become abnormally activated in the cytoplasm, and this, in turn, leads to functional and morphological disorders. A deeper understanding of the nature of oxidative stress and its role in the development of AIT may help identify new methods for its assessment and expand the therapeutic range for this disease. The review discusses oxidative stress, which is the accumulation of active damaging agents (free radicals, pro-oxidants, reactive oxygen species) that initiate cell damage and lead to the development of various pathological conditions. It is based on free radical oxidation of fatty acids, or so-called lipid peroxidation.*

Keywords: *oxidative stress, hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, thyroid gland, autoimmunity.*

РИСК АУТОИММУННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ ВО ВРЕМЯ ОКИСЛИТЕЛЬНОГО СТРЕССА

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Аннотация. В настоящее время известно большое количество социально значимых заболеваний, при которых повреждение тканей сопровождается развитием окислительного стресса. Свободные радикалы играют решающую роль в развитии этих заболеваний. Подобные процессы происходят под воздействием источников ионизирующего излучения, а также при бактериальных инфекциях. Недавно появились научные данные, указывающие на значительную роль окислительного стресса в развитии аутоиммунных тиреопатий. Предполагается, что синтез тиреоидных гормонов зависит от концентрации H_2O_2 , которая в силу своей высокой токсичности должна находиться в строгом соответствии с активностью антиоксидантных систем. В норме многие биохимически неблагоприятные процессы происходят на апикальной мембране тироцита, что позволяет ограничить действие свободных радикалов и избежать разрушения клеток. Однако при патологических состояниях ферментативные системы нарушаются, а их компоненты аномально активируются в цитоплазме, что, в свою очередь, приводит к функциональным и морфологическим нарушениям. Более глубокое понимание природы окислительного стресса и его роли в развитии АИТ может помочь определить новые методы его оценки и расширить терапевтический диапазон этого заболевания. В обзоре обсуждается окислительный стресс, представляющий собой накопление активных повреждающих агентов (свободных радикалов, прооксидантов, активных форм кислорода), инициирующих повреждение клеток и приводящих к развитию различных патологических состояний. В его основе лежит свободнорадикальное окисление жирных кислот, или так называемое перекисное окисление липидов.

Ключевые слова: окислительный стресс, гипотиреоз, гипертиреоз, щитовидная железа, аутоиммунитет.

Introduction. Most researchers share the opinion that autoimmune thyropathies (AIT) are multifactorial diseases caused by a complex interaction of genetic, hormonal and environmental factors that provoke the development of inadequate immune responses against the thyroid gland (TG) at different levels and initiate a long-term autoimmune reaction. Oxidative stress plays an important role in the pathogenesis of autoimmune thyroid diseases. In this regard, the purpose of this review was to analyze the latest research on this topic and substantiate the connection between oxidative stress and autoimmune thyroid diseases. It is known that oxidative stress (oxidative stress, in English - oxidative stress, OS) is involved in the pathogenesis of such important diseases as atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic diseases and oncological processes. Inflammatory-dystrophic changes in tissues, in these conditions, are associated with the attack of free radicals from the internal environment of the body, where, for various reasons, their increased concentration occurs and is maintained. Oxygen free radicals negatively affect biological molecules such as lipids, proteins and DNA. However, we should not forget about the important role of OS in the framework of physiological adaptation and regulation of intracellular signaling [1]. The pathogenesis of oxidative stress in OS is defined as an imbalance between the production of pro-oxidative substances and the protective antioxidant system. The most important pro-oxidant substances are reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS). The study of biomarkers of oxidative stress allows us to understand the mechanism of this condition and the pathogenesis of diseases. Currently, oxidative substrates obtained as a result of exposure to free radicals are used as markers of OS, namely: products of lipid peroxidation (lipid peroxide, malondialdehyde (MDA) and 4-hydroxynonenal), isoprostane, as a product of free radical oxidation of arachidonic acid, timineglycol and 8-hydroxyguanine – as indicators of oxidative DNA damage [1]. If we talk about free radicals, then these are atoms and molecules that have unpaired electrons. Free radicals are usually unstable and very active because the unpaired electrons tend to pair with other molecules. Reactive oxygen species include superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, hydrogen peroxide and hypochlorous acid. The first three substances are formed in vivo mainly by the mitochondrial respiratory chain during the oxidative metabolism of energy substrates. They are regulators of redox-sensitive pathways involved in cellular homeostasis and influence several transcription factors, in addition to the endogenous antioxidant pool [2]. Reactive forms of nitrogen include peroxyxynitrite, which is formed as a result of the reaction of nitric oxide (NO) with

superoxide and nitrosoperoxycarbonate, formed as a result of the reaction of peroxy nitrite with carbon dioxide. ROS and AFA are important links in pathogenesis in the development of various diseases. Among them, free radicals play a special pathogenetic role, i.e. superoxide anion and hydroxyl radical (due to their high chemical activity) [3]. For aerobic organisms, a mechanism for removing reactive oxygen species is necessary to maintain life. Therefore, in the process of evolution, various antioxidant defense mechanisms have developed. The antioxidant system is represented by an enzymatic link and non-enzymatic antioxidants (vitamin E, C, CoQ (coenzyme Q)). The enzymatic component of the antioxidant system consists of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase and glutathione peroxidase. The main mechanism of the body's defense against these ROS is the enzyme SOD; its activity is usually sufficient to inactivate them at the site of formation, preventing diffusion in the environment of tissue macromolecules. Dismutation of superoxide anion radicals under the influence of SOD in biological tissues leads to the formation of hydrogen peroxide, which can easily penetrate cell membranes. Hydrogen peroxide is detected during phagocytosis, during the work of mitochondria and microsomes [4]. In the presence of transition metal ions (eg Fe²⁺), hydrogen peroxide can produce a highly reactive hydroxyl radical (*OH). This process is prevented by the main highly active enzymes of the body's antioxidant defense: catalase and glutathione peroxidase. Oxidative stress and thyroid hormones Among all the hormones that act on the antioxidant system, thyroid hormones play a particularly important role, since both hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism are associated with OS [3]. However, the mechanism of OS in these 2 conditions is different: increased production of ROS in hyperthyroidism and low availability of the antioxidant system in hypothyroidism [5]. Thyroid hormones as such can act as oxidants and damage DNA, probably through the phenolic group, which is similar to the activity of steroidal estrogens [6]. Other mechanisms may be involved, particularly increased expression of nitric oxide synthase (NOS) with excess production of NO and activation of hepatic NF- κ B (transcription factor NF- κ B, nuclear factor kappa-bi) with a subsequent increase in the concentration of cytokines that induce AFC products. On the other hand, mechanisms regulated by thyroid hormones finely regulate oxidative status through feedback. Among them, the role of the proteins UCP-2 and UCP-3 (uncoupling proteins 2 and 3) is emphasized. Data obtained from plants and animals indicate that these molecules have antioxidant activity [7–9]. However, only triiodothyronine (T3) appears to regulate UCP, while thyroxine (T4) has no effect [10, 11]. In theory, this could be

used to treat "low T3 syndrome." On the contrary, estrogens increase ROS production by suppressing UCP [12]. Studies have shown that thyroid hormones affect the lipid metabolism of rat tissues and, consequently, their susceptibility to OS. However, conflicting effects have been noted between exposure to T3 and T4. In rat liver, T3-induced hyperthyroidism has been found to be associated with altered indices of lipid peroxidation, including increased levels of thiobarbituric active substances (TBARS) and lipid hydroperoxides, which are by-products of lipid peroxidation [13–15]. In contrast, no change in the increase in TBARS was found in homogenized livers of hyperthyroid rats by T4 administration over a 4-week period [16]. No significant changes in the amount of TBARS or lipid hydroperoxides were observed in the testes of adult hyperthyroid rats; however, hyperthyroidism promoted protein oxidation in the testes, as evidenced by increased protein-bound carbonyls [17]. At the systemic level, hyperthyroidism is associated with decreased circulating concentrations of α -tocopherol [18, 19] and CoQ10 (coenzyme Q10) [19, 20] in humans. CoQ10 was markedly increased in hypothyroidism and its concentration was shown to correlate with the severity of hypothyroidism [20]. Thus, it can be a sensitive marker of thyroid disease in cases where the interpretation of hormonal studies is questioned in various conditions (due to blood sampling errors and laboratory interference). On the other hand, the results of studies on the relationship between hypothyroidism and OS in humans are contradictory. It has been suggested that in patients with AIT and hypothyroidism, the pro-oxidant environment may play a role in the development of atherosclerosis. The increase in OS can be explained not only by a decrease in the concentration of antioxidants, but also by changes in lipid metabolism, since a significant relationship was found between the concentration of MDA and LDL, total cholesterol and triglycerides. The overall antioxidant status was similar in manifest hypothyroidism in the outcome of AIT, subclinical hypothyroidism and in the control group. Other studies have also confirmed an increase in MDA with lipid peroxidation in both overt hypothyroidism and subclinical hypothyroidism [21]. Data on other indicators are more contradictory. Regarding PON-1 (serum paraoxonase/arylesterase 1, also known as A-esterase), a decrease in the activity of this enzyme was observed in both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism [22], while other studies [23] did not find significant differences in groups in relation to the control group. Not only increased concentrations of TBARS, but also increased concentrations of antioxidant substances such as SOD, catalase, and vitamin E have been reported [24]. All of these parameters were correlated with T3 concentration, and the correlation between T3 concentration and catalase

remained statistically significant even when values were adjusted for total cholesterol. An increase in TBARS was detected both in overt hypothyroidism and in subclinical [23, 25], however, in other studies these results were not confirmed [23, 26].

Conclusion. We still have much to learn about the cellular mechanisms and interactions in autoimmune thyroid diseases before we can fully understand the pathophysiology of these diseases. According to the available literature data, it can be argued that OS plays an important role in the progression of autoimmune inflammation. Thyroid hormones may have a protective role by influencing antioxidant levels; on the other hand, hypothyroidism can worsen OS. The study of OS markers such as MDA and lipid peroxidation products can be used in the future to confirm the diagnosis and prescribe adequate treatment for patients with autoimmune thyroid diseases [48]. Antioxidants may play a positive role in the correction of metabolic disorders in thyroid diseases, but further research on this topic is needed.

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